

Welcome page

A. Survey Introduction

Thank you for your interest in our research!

Please complete our five-minute survey, where we'll ask you about your professional background and experience, as well as your use of AI in IDEs.

By participating in our survey, not only will you be helping us with our research, but you'll also get the chance to win one of five USD 50 Amazon Gift Cards or JetBrains product subscription. We'll randomly pick the winners from among those questionnaires that are filled out completely with meaningful answers. Remember to enter your contact details to be eligible for the prize draw.

B. Please review our Terms and Conditions below.

I agree to the General Research Terms and Conditions

C. Please provide your contact details.

Note: Your email address will be used to send invitations for research.

First name:

Email address:

D. In which country or region do you currently reside?

E. Which prize would you like to get if you win?

(Radio button, select one)

Six-month JetBrains All Products Pack subscription

USD 50 Amazon Gift Card

I would prefer not to get any prize

General questions

1. Which of the following best describe your job role? (Checkbox, select multiple)

Developer / Programmer / Software Engineer

- DevOps Engineer / Infrastructure Developer
- Architect
- Tester / QA Engineer
- Technical Support Specialist
- Data Analyst / Data Engineer / Data Scientist
- Business Analyst
- Technical Writer
- Team Lead
- Researcher
- Systems Analyst
- Product Manager / Marketing Manager
- UX / UI Designer
- CIO / CEO / CTO
- Developer Advocate
- Instructor / Teacher / Tutor
- Intern
- Student
- Other, please specify: _____

**2. How many full years of professional coding experience do you have?
(Radio button, select one)**

- Less than 1 year
- 1–2 years
- 3–5 years
- 6–10 years
- 11–16 years
- 17 years or more
- I don't have any professional coding experience

**3. Which of the following AI tools have you used for coding and related tasks?
(Checkbox, select multiple)**

- Aide by CodeStory
- Amazon CodeWhisperer

- Anthropic Claude
- Blackbox AI
- ChatGPT
- Code GPT plugin in VS Code
- CodeGPT plugin in JetBrains IDEs (IntelliJ IDEA, PyCharm, PhpStorm, etc.)
- Code Llama
- Codeium
- Qodo (previously Codium)
- Cursor
- Devin
- Gemini Code Assist
- Google Gemini (previously Bard)
- GitHub Copilot
- GitLab Duo
- IntelliPHP
- JetBrains AI Assistant
- Microsoft Copilot
- OpenHands
- Project IDX
- Replit AI
- Sourcegraph Cody
- Sourcery
- Android Studio Bot
- Tabby
- Tabnine
- Visual Studio IntelliCode
- Zed
- Windsurf Editor
- Custom local AI tool for coding and development
- Other, please specify: _____
- None

**4. What is your experience with AI tools for coding?
(Radio button, select one)**

I'm not aware of such tools (**exclude**)

I've never used such tools and I don't want to try any (**exclude**)

I've never used such tools, but I'd like to try them (**exclude**)

I tried using them for a while but stopped >>>

I use them once in a while >>>

I use them regularly >>>

Other >>>

**5. For how long have you been using AI tools for coding?
(Radio button, select one)**

- Less than 1 week
- 1–2 weeks
- 3–4 weeks
- 2–3 months
- 4–6 months
- 7–12 months
- More than 1 year

Workflow questions (*first 9 presented in random order*):

1. Overall, how do you feel about your experience with the AI tools for coding that you use in your development workflow?

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

2. How has the introduction of AI tools for coding affected your overall productivity?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

3. How have these AI tools affected the proportion of your working time spent coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

4. How has the frequency of context switching (switching between different tasks or thought processes) changed because of your use of AI tools for coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change

- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

5. How has the quality of the code you produce changed because of your use of AI tools for coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

6. How has the readability of the code you write changed because of your use of AI tools for coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

7. How has the frequency of editing or modifying your own code changed because of your use of AI tools for coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

8. How has your frequency of use of code from external sources (e.g. libraries, online examples, or AI-suggested code) changed since you started using AI tools for coding?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

9. Since you first started using AI tools for coding, how has your reliance on them for your coding tasks changed?

- Significantly decreased
- Slightly decreased
- No change
- Slightly increased
- Significantly increased

10. Can you provide a specific example of how AI tools for coding have impacted your workflow?

- [Open-ended response]

Thank you message

Thank you for completing this survey!